

VIEWER ADVISORY

Blood/Gore

This panel may contain visual representations of blood and gore.

Violence

This panel may contain scenes of violence.

Mild Nudity

This panel may contain characters displaying mild nudity.

Patterned flashes

This panel may contain patterned or random light flashes.

Be also aware of potential spoilers!

Sound check:

Japanese animation for T.V.

OPening credit sequence

THE ANIME OP

a Corpus Study of Anison

Anime song = songs that appear in anime

MOTIVATION

GLOBAL APPEAL

Popularity both in Japan and abroad.
Nostalgic item that may define a whole generation.

RELEVANCY

Relevant to the study of contemporary pop song form.
Similarities and dissimilarities worth studying.

INTERDISCIPLINARITY

Offers interdisciplinarity with media studies and
non-western studies.

RESEARCH GAP

It is an otherwise overlooked genre of media in the
field of pop music theory.

START

GATHER DATA

Source 1: MyAnimeList.net top 200 most popular anime as of 2024.
Source 2: Japan Billboard Hot Animation between 2013-2024.

PRUNING

Deduplication, removing film OSTs.
348 tracks total.

ENCODE TRACKS

Analyze form, visual content and demographics.
Cross-checking.

THEORIZE

Make sense of the results.

END

CORPORA COMPOSITION AND METHODOLOGY

GENERAL OP CHARACTERISTICS

VISUAL

Introduces the title

Presents main and secondary characters

Credits authors and producing team

Shows snapshots of scenes

MUSICAL

90 seconds in length

Features any genre of music

Genre of music hints at genre of anime

Vocalist sex hints at main character's sex

ORIGINAL

00:00	Intro
00:46	Verse 1
01:08	Pre-chorus 1
01:29	Chorus 1
01:54	Post-chorus 1
02:04	Verse 2
02:26	Pre-chorus 2
02:48	Chorus 2
03:12	Bridge
03:33	Solo
03:55	Chorus 3
04:30	Outro

OP

00:00	Intro
00:11	Verse
00:33	Pre-chorus
00:54	Chorus
01:19	Outro

FORM CHARACTERISTICS

1

intro

2

verse
prechorus
chorus

3

outro

FORM CHARACTERISTICS

1

CALL

2

verse
prechorus
chorus

3

outro

FORM CHARACTERISTICS

1

THE CALL

CALL CHARACTERISTICS

- Texturally busy and/or timbrally bright (Lavengood 2020)
- Usually part of a chorus/refrain/hook
- Sometimes a distinct section
- Visually will show title and main character

1-part call

2-part call

Peres 2016

CALL STYLES

UNIQUE CALL (27% of corpus)

- Only heard once
- Can be musical: tutti chords, guitar lick, piano arpeggio
- Can be non-musical: spoken voice, guitar noise, sound effects

Jojo's Bizarre Adventure (Part 4): Diamond is Unbreakable (2016)

HYPER CALL (10% of corpus)

- The rarest of all call styles
- Related to Unique Call
- Much more energetic or extremely noisy (harmony may not make sense)
- Most hyper calls in the study feature sound effects, guitar noise or synths.

Highschool of the Dead Season 1 (2010)

CLIMAX CALL (23% of corpus)

- High-intensity section, or “climax” section
- Can be part of a chorus, refrain, hook...
- Will be heard later again

Kaguya-sama: Love is War Season 1 (2019)

ISOLATED CALL (24% of corpus)

- Related to Climax Call
- Climax section is depicted with minimal accompaniment (drums usually absent)
- Vocals are the most commonly isolated (acoustically positioned in the foreground of the mix)
- Guitar is the next most commonly isolated instrument

Fullmetal Alchemist: Brotherhood Season 1 (2009)

1

CALL

2

verse
prechorus
chorus

3

outro

2

THE OP FORMAT

OP FORMAT

1

call

2

verse
prechorus
chorus

3

outro

postchorus
bridge
interlude
solo
breakdown

OP FORMAT

1

call

2

verse
prechorus
chorus

3

postchorus
bridge
interlude + outro
solo
breakdown

OP FORMAT

OP FORMAT

Spy x Family Season 1 (2022)

STANDARD OP FORMAT (72% of corpus)

3

THE VISUALS

1

call

Main character
Abstract items
Title

2

verse

Main character
Side characters
Anime art style

3

prechorus

Antagonists
Villains

4

chorus

Action
Fighting
Running

5

outro

Wide shot
Landscape
Characters in group

VISUAL FORMULA

Musical

Visual

Sword Art Online Season 1 (2012)

SUMMARY: ANNOTATED EXAMPLE

4

CONCLUSION

SELECTED BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Attas, Robin. 2015.** “Form as Process: The Buildup Introduction in Popular Music.” *Music Theory Spectrum* 37 (2): 275–96.
- Billboard Japan. 2013.** “Hot Animation.” Accessed December 15, 2023.
- de Clercq, Trevor. 2017.** “Embracing Ambiguity in the Analysis of Form in Pop/Rock Music, 1982–1991.” *MTO* 23 (3).
- Ensign, Jeffrey S. 2015.** “Form In Popular Song, 1990-2009.” PhD diss., University of North Texas.
- Goldmark, Daniel Ira. 2001.** “Happy harmonies: Music and the Hollywood animated cartoon.” PhD diss., University of California.
- Gray, Jonathan. 1995.** *Showtime: Television, Entertainment, and Society*. Oxford University Press.
- Lavengood, Megan. 2020.** “The Cultural Significance of Timbre Analysis: A Case Study in 1980s Pop Music, Texture, and Narrative.” *MTO* 26 (3).
- Malawey, Victoria. 2020.** *A Blaze of Light in Every Word: Analyzing the Popular Singing Voice*. Oxford University Press.
- Martin, Nathan John. 2024.** “Corpus Studies and ‘Close Listening.’” *Music Analysis* 43 no. 2: 191–246.
- McClary, Susan. 1991.** *Feminine Endings: Music, Gender, and Sexuality*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Middleton, Richard. 2002.** *Studying Popular Music*. Open University Press.
- MyAnimeList. n.d.** “Top Anime by Popularity.” Accessed December 15, 2023.
- Nazare, Tan. 2023.** “The Anime Sound: An Analytical and Semiotic Study of Contemporary Anime Music.” MA thesis, McGill University.
- Neumeyer, David. 2015.** *Meaning and Interpretation of Music in Cinema*. Indiana University Press.
- Nobile, Drew. 2020.** *Form as Harmony in Rock Music*. Oxford University Press.
- Peres, Asaf. 2016.** “The Sonic Dimension as Dramatic Driver in 21st-Century Pop Music.” PhD diss., University of Michigan.
- Ramage, Maxwell. 2023.** “The Royal Road Progression in Japanese Popular Music.” *Music Theory Spectrum* 45 (2): 238–56.
- Scoggin, Lisa, and Dana Plank. 2023.** *The Intersection of Animation, Video Games, and Music*. Routledge.
- Summach, Jay. 2012.** “Form in Top-20 Rock Music, 1955-89.” PhD diss., Yale University.
- Temperley, David. 2018.** *The Musical Language of Rock*. Oxford University Press.

THANK YOU
